

**A STUDY ON ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF WORKING CAPITAL
MANAGEMENT ON PROFITABILITY OF THE SELECTED TEXTILE
COMPANIES IN INDIA**

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ABSTRACT

To manage working capital of the business is one of the difficult task of financial management. The present research paper tried to assess the impact of working capital management over the profit efficiency. The study was based on secondary data and contains analysis of 5 years that is from 2016 to 2021. Return on Assets (ROA) is used to quantify profitability, whereas Average Collection Period (ACP), Inventory Conversion Period (ICP), Average Payment Period (APP), and Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) were served as working capital management proxies. Debt Ratio, Current Ratio, Sales Growth, and Firm Size were taken as controlled variables. To assess the influence of these variables on profitability, descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and regression analysis were employed in this study. The findings of correlation analysis show that ROA has negative relation with ACP, ICP, CCC and DR while ROA is positively related with APP, current Ratio and growth.

Key words: *Working Capital Management, Profit efficiency, Textile Industry, India*

INTRODUCTION

Modern financial management accept the importance of working capital and accept that it is too difficult to manage the working capital. Working capital is that capital which is required to manage the day to day routine transactions of the business. Without effective management of working capital, it is quite difficult to do smooth running of the everyday transactions of the business. The holding period for working capital is generally ranges from 6 months to period of one year. During this time, it converted into its various components. Working capital has its own importance in financial management and it brings fixed capital into working conditions and therefore, the present study focuses on the assessment of its impact over profit making capacity of the business concern.¹

Textile originally meant a woven or knitted fabric made from yarn. But apart from fibre, yarn and fabric or other products which are made from these compounds is defined as textile. Fabrics are also linked with the

production of clothing. Fibre is a raw material for textiles that can be natural or man-made. The textile industry is an industry that includes sections such as research, design, development, production and distribution of textiles, fabrics and clothing. The textile industry has essential labour-intensive nature capabilities, provides job in the short term and helps in growth of Indian economy. The sector offers unprecedented employment opportunities, especially for people in rural areas. The textile sector in India accounts for 10% of the country's manufacturing production, 5% of India's goods domestic product and 13% of India's exports earnings. Manufacturing progress is also likely to help eliminate regional disparities across the country by supporting rural and semi-urban industries and providing unskilled labour employment.⁴

Working capital management and profitability are intertwined in some way. There are numerous study studies on this relationship in India's various sectors. Working capital management is an essential component of any company's operations. As a result, working capital management is critical in the textile industry. The prime objective of the present research paper is to identify whether "working capital management has any effect on the profitability of India's textile sector or not"

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. **Zbigniew golas (2020)** conducted a study on Impact of working capital management on business profitability: Evidence from the polish dairy industry. The analyses found that in large companies, an increase in ROA is driven by a reduction in DSIs and CCCs.
2. **Ahmed chand, Sadafakram, Hamza Murad and Luqman Karen (2019)** conducted a research on "The impact of working capital management on firm profitability: A comparison between seasonal and non-seasonal business. The study concluded that working capital management has negative impact on the profitability. The study found that there is no difference between seasonal and non- seasonal businesses in terms of WCM and firm profitability.
3. **Dina korent & silvije orsag (2018)** conducted research on, The impact of working capital management on profitability of Croatian software companies. The findings show that after controlling for characteristics of the company and macroeconomic conditions working capital management affects the profitability of Croatian software firms.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of the present study is to identify and analyse the impact of working capital management on the profitability of the selected textile companies in India.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

1. **Sample Period:** The period of study is of five years ranges from 2016-2017 to 2020-2021.

2. **Sample Size:** The researcher selects five textile companies randomly that is Arvind Ltd., Vardhman textile Ltd., Welspun India Ltd., Raymond Ltd. and Trident Ltd.
3. **Data Source:** present data source of the study is based on secondary data. The basic information about the research were taken from the journals, magazines, articles, newspaper and the reference books. The financial data of the selected textile companies are taken from the published annual reports on the websites of the concern companies.
4. **Key Variables:** To examine the impact of WCM on the profitability of the selected Textile Companies in India, dependent and independent both variables are used. Here the researchers have selected the one dependent and six independent variables along with one control variable. The following table shows the list of variables taken under the study.

NO.	Type of Variable	Name of the Variable	Measurement	Code
1.	Dependent Variable	Return of Assets	Net income/Total Assets	ROA
2.	Independent Variable	Average Collection Period	(Account Receivable/ Net Sales) *365	ACP
		Inventory Conversion Period	(Inventory/Cost of sales) *365	ICP
		Average Payment Period	(Account Payables/Cost of Sales) *365	APP
		Cash Conversion Period	ACP+ICP+APP	CCC
		Debt Ratio	Total Liabilities/Total Assets	DR
		Current Ratio	Current Assets/Current Liabilities	CR
3.	Control Variable	Sales Growth	$(Sales_t - Sales_{t-1}) / Sales_{t-1}$	Growth

HYPOTHESIS

H₀: There is no significant association between Return on Assets and Current Ratio of the selected textile companies in India

H₀: There is no significant relationship between Return on Assets and Average Collection Period of the selected textile companies in India

H₀: There is no significant relationship between Return on Assets and Inventory Conversion Period of the selected textile companies in India

H₀: There is no significant relationship between Return on Assets and Average Payment Period of the selected textile companies in India

H₀: There is no significant relationship between Return on Assets and Debt Ratio of the selected textile companies in India

H₀: There is no significant relationship between Return on Assets and Cash Conversion Period of the selected textile companies in India

DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS ANALYSIS

VARIABLE	Mean	Median	SD	Minimum	Maximum
ROA	0.81	0.81	0.1192	0.43	0.99
ACP	53.31	46.29	21.6317	21.63	122.04
ICP	158.62	149.38	69.1609	44.68	319.32
APP	75.66	53.91	61.913	25.6	247.15
CCC	136.31	114.02	83.76853	14.76	351.49
DR	0.29	0.16	0.32938	0.05	1.31
CR	6.95	1.08	27.7261	0.9	140
GROWTH	0.01	0.02	0.1433	-0.45	0.26

Descriptive statistics of the selected textile companies shows that average return on assets for businesses is 8.12 percent of total assets, with median of 8.1 percent and standard deviation value of 11.92 percent, Which means that productivity estimates can vary by 8.12 percent from plan to plan on both sides. Its minimum and maximum values are 4.33 percent and 9.9 percent, respectively.

The Average Collection Period (ACP) is used to assess collection policy. For the sampled firms, the ACP average value is 53.31 days. The ACP is interpreted as 53 days on average for organisations in the sample to convert credit sales into cash. for the firms selected as a sample, the minimum and maximum ACP values are 21.63 and 122.04 days, respectively.

The inventory conversion period is adopted as a substitute measure for inventory policy. The ICP's average value of is of 158.62 days, which means, the sample firms need on average 158.62 to sell out their inventory. As shown in the above stated table, the inventory holding period's standard deviation is 69.16 days and the

inventory holding time frame stays between 44.58 and 319.32 days as minimum and maximum values respectively.

The average payment period performs as the substitute for the payment policy. The average value of APP is 75.66 days. The standard deviation of APP for the selected firms is 53.91 days. The period spans between 25.6 and 247.15 days respectively.

Moreover, cash conversion cycle, is 136.31 days on average and the SD is 114.02 days. The minimum value is 14.76 days indicates that a firm documents a large inventory turnover before making a single payment for credit purchases from credit sales. It signifies that the average collection period/or the ACP of the firm is long. On the other side the time for cash conversion period is 351.49 days which is a considerably long.

The above stated table also covers descriptive statistics for control variables used in the study. To investigate the firm's size and its relationship to profitability.

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

Pearson's correlation grid is used to analyse the relationship between variables, such as working capital management and firm financial performance (profitability measure).

	<i>ROA</i>	<i>ACP</i>	<i>ICP</i>	<i>APP</i>	<i>CCC</i>	<i>DR</i>	<i>CR</i>	<i>GROWTH</i>
<i>ROA</i>	1							
<i>ACP</i>	-0.63	1						
<i>ICP</i>	-0.10	-0.32	1					
<i>APP</i>	0.21	0.06	0.10	1				
<i>CCC</i>	-0.41	-0.05	0.66	-0.63	1			
<i>DR</i>	-0.16	0.51	-0.65	-0.31	-0.17	1		
<i>CR</i>	0.19	-0.05	-0.09	0.01	-0.10	0.003	1	
<i>GROWTH</i>	0.69	-0.60	-0.16	-0.33	-0.04	0.03	0.21	1

Above stated table indicates that ROA is negatively related with ACP, ICP, CCC and DR. The relation between ROA and ACP is negative and consistent with the view that to increase the profitability by enhancing the sales one needs to accelerate more money to renew the inventory, and for this the clients has to take less time to pay their bills. ROA is positively related with APP, current Ratio and growth.

REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Here, to estimate the casual relationship between the profitability and other dependent variables the Regression analysis is employed.

Relationship between CR and ROA:

SUMMARY OUTPUT

<i>Regression Statistics</i>				
Multiple R	0.19			
R Square	0.038			
Adjusted R Square	-0.002			
Standard Error	0.11			
Observations	25			

ANOVA				
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>
Regression	1	0.013	0.013	0.93
Residual	23	0.32	0.014	
Total	24	0.34		

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	0.8	0.024	32.69	8.75
CR	0.0008	0.0008	0.96	0.34

The CR and ROA have a positive association, as shown in the regression table above. The p value in the table above exceeds the 0.05 level of significance. As a result. The Null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative will be rejected and the correlation between CR and ROA seems positive and significant.

Relationship between ACP and ROA:

SUMMARY OUTPUT

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.63
R Square	0.4
Adjusted R Square	0.37
Standard Error	0.094
Observations	25

ANOVA

		<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>
Regression	1	0.13		0.13	15.54
Residual	23	0.2		0.008	
Total	24	0.34			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	0.99	0.05	19.6	7.5
ACP	-0.0035	0.0008	-3.94	0.0006

The regression values stated in above table, indicates that ACP and ROA have a negative association. The p value in the table above is less than the 0.05 significance level. As a result, the null hypothesis will be rejected and the alternative hypothesis will be accepted. As a result, ACP and ROA have a substantial association.

Relationship between ICP and ROA:

SUMMARY OUTPUT

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.1
R Square	0.012
Adjusted R Square	-0.03
Standard Error	0.12
Observations	25

ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>
Regression	1	0.004	0.004	0.28
Residual	23	0.33	0.014	
Total	24	0.3414		

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	0.84	0.061	13.65	1.6
ICP	-0.0001	0.0003	-0.53	0.6

The ICP and ROA have a positive association, as shown in the regression table above. The p value in the table above exceeds the 0.05 level of significance. As a result, the null hypothesis accepted while rejecting the alternative. As a result, the correlation seems positive and significant between ICP and ROA.

Relationship between APP and ROA:

SUMMARY OUTPUT

<i>Regression Statistics</i>				
Multiple R		0.21		
R Square		0.046		
Adjusted R Square		0.004		
Standard Error		0.11		
Observations		25		

<i>ANOVA</i>				
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>
Regression	1	0.015	0.015	1.12
Residual	23	0.32	0.014	
Total	24	0.34		

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	0.78	0.038	20.51	2.76
APP	0.0004	0.0003	1.058	0.3

The APP and ROA have a positive association, as indicated in the regression table above. The p value in the table above exceeds the 0.05 level of significance. As a result, we will accept the null hypothesis while rejecting the alternative. As a result, the correlation between APP and ROA is positive and significant.

Relationship between CCC and ROA:

SUMMARY OUTPUT

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.41
R Square	0.17
Adjusted R Square	0.13
Standard Error	0.11
Observations	25

ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>
Regression	1	0.058	0.058	4.73
Residual	23	0.28	0.012	
Total	24	0.34		

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	0.89	0.043	20.74	2.18
CCC	-0.0005	0.0002	-2.17	0.04

The regression table indicates that CCC and ROA have a negative association. The p value in the table above is less than the 0.05 significance level. As a result, the null hypothesis will be rejected and the alternative hypothesis will be accepted. As a result, CCC and ROA have a substantial association.

Relationship between Debt Ratio and ROA:

SUMMARY OUTPUT

Regression Statistics

Multiple R	0.16
R Square	0.02
Adjusted R Square	-0.01
Standard Error	0.12
Observations	25

ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>
Regression	1	0.009	0.009	0.64
Residual	23	0.33	0.014	
Total	24	0.34		

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	0.82	0.032	25.5	2.27
DR	-0.05	0.074	-0.8	0.43

The Debt ratio and ROA have a positive association, as shown in the regression table above. The p value in the table above exceeds the 0.05 level of significance. As a result, we will accept the null hypothesis while rejecting the alternative. As a result, the correlation between Debt ratio and ROA is positive and significant.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study is entirely based on the secondary data, opted from the firm's annual reports and hence the secondary data itself has its limitation with the limited area.

The study period is of 5 years from 2016-17 to 2020-21 and therefore, the research only shows the results for that period.

Interpretation based on ratio analysis is based on historical costs which is a limitation in itself.

FUTURE SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The aim of the study is to find the significant impact of working capital on the company's profitability of the selected textile companies in India. There is still a scope to examine the same impact on the Earning Per Share, Liquidity, short term liquidity position of the firm.

The present study aims to find out the impact of working capital on the profitability of the selected textile companies in India still there is a scope to examine the impact of working capital on the Earning Per Share, liquidity, short term solvency of the firm.

CONCLUSION

As per the findings of the current study, maintaining an effective level of working capital is critical in all industries, not only for the textile industry. ROA has a negative association with ACP, ICP, CCC and DR, according to the correlation analysis. Similarly, ROA has positive relation with the APP, CR and sales growth. CCC has a negative relationship with ROA, implying that a greater CCC reduces profitability and vice versa.

To check the significant impact on the profitability, the regression analysis was used. The findings show that ROA has positive relationship between ICP, APP, CR and DR and negative relationship between ACP and CCC.

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